

DEMO: Human Sales Ability Estimation Service Based on Interview Video Analysis

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Abstract — The ability to sell products and services is crucial for any business to succeed, and the ability to identify good salespeople is equally important. Nonetheless, recognizing the right candidate with outstanding sales skills during a job interview can prove to be challenging. To tackle this issue, a human sales ability estimation service based on interview video analysis was developed. This service uses artificial intelligence and computer vision techniques to analyze the video of a job interview and assess the participant's sales ability. This service allows the participant to record a self-interview using the website. The participant should answer predefined questions related to personality analysis and the sales topic. After a few minutes, the web service used the trained model to access the participant's abilities to work in sales and print out the classification results. It also shows the participant's personality traits according to the OCEAN model. Using this service can help the recruiting manager to decide between hiring the participant. It also can be used to select a group of participants and nominate them for the second stage of the test. Also, this service gives valuable information about the participant's personality and soft skills which is crucial in the sales field.